

Ring Size Determines the Conformation, Global Aromaticity and Photophysical Properties of Macrocyclic Oligofurans

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In Memory of François Diederich

Abstract: In π -conjugated macrocycles, there is a trade-off between the global and local expression of effects such as aromaticity, with the outcome of the trade-off determined by the geometry and aromaticity of the constituent units. Compared with other aromatic rings, furan aromaticity is relatively low, and therefore global effects in macrocyclic furans are expected to be more pronounced. Following our introduction of macrocyclic oligofuran, we present the first synthesis of a series of π -conjugated bifuran macrocycles of various ring sizes, from trimer to hexamer, and characterize them using both computational and experimental methods. The properties of macrocyclic oligofurans change considerably with size: The smaller trimer is rigid, non-emissive and planar as revealed by its single crystal structure, and displays global antiaromaticity, while the larger pentamer and hexamer are flexible, emissive, have non-planar structures, and exhibit local aromaticity. The results are supported by NICS and ACID calculations that indicate the global antiaromaticity of planar furan macrocycles, and by transient absorption measurements showing sharp absorption bands for the trimer and only the internal conversion decay pathway.

Introduction

π -Conjugated cyclic oligomers with well-defined diameters have been the subject of many studies over the last few decades because of their host–guest capabilities, potential to form supramolecular assemblies, and unique electronic and optical properties.^[1] The angular constraints on the repeat unit dictate the size and conformation of the macrocycle, which in turn affect its optical and electronic properties.^[2] For example, the least strained size for macrocyclic thiophenes (**C-nT**) is $n = 10–14$, whereas meta-connected phenylenes produce 6-mer macrocycles.^[3] Thus, the introduction of new building units is expected to result in new conformations and consequently new properties.

Macrocyclic α -oligothiophenes, first introduced by Bäuerle's group, have been reported in sizes ranging from **C-8T** to **C-35T** (Scheme 1).^[4] Whereas acetylene-spaced macrocyclic thiophenes are planar and reportedly self-assemble into wire-like structures,^[5] oligothiophene macrocycles with no spacers are distorted from planarity. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations suggest a spiderlike conformation for **C-8T**,^[6] and the crystal structure of **C-10T** reveals interring dihedral twisting of 26–34°.^[7] Such twisting is expected to decrease intramolecular π -conjugation and negatively affect intermolecular interactions, both of which are crucial for optoelectronic applications. In principle, **C-nT** are expected to display a global antiaromaticity, as they

represent a $4n\pi$ macrocyclic system. However, since thiophenes have significant local aromaticity, and they are distorted out-of-plane, such global antiaromaticity is not observed. Global antiaromaticity was previously reported for macrocyclic systems, such as porphyrins and polyradicaloid aromatics,^[8] but is less common in α,α' -connected macrocycles.^[9]

Following the introduction of linear α -oligofurans, which display good π -conjugation, strong fluorescence, and high planarity/rigidity compared with their thiophene analogues,^[10] we began to study macrocyclic α -oligofurans (**C-nF**).^[11] Our calculations predicted that small macrocyclic oligofurans (6–8-mers) should be planar, in sharp contrast with **C-nT**; furthermore, such macrocycles are expected to display stronger π -conjugation and smaller HOMO–LUMO gaps, and the smaller macrocycles in the series should also exhibit lower strain energy than their **C-nT** analogues. Recent calculations indicate that small **C-nF** should display triplet Baird aromaticity.^[12] The relative instability of oligofurans impeded the synthesis of such macrocycles. To overcome this issue, we previously designed and introduced 2,2'-bifuran-3,3'-dicarboximide (**L-nBFI**) oligomers and polymers, which we found to be significantly more stable than the parent furans.^[13] Following the introduction of this building block, we successfully synthesized and introduced the first macrocyclic oligofuran, **C-4BFI** (Scheme 1),^[14] and showed it to be planar and highly conjugated. Recently, a second macrocyclic oligofuran, bearing ester groups was reported.^[15]

Following our initial investigation of **C-4BFI**, we were interested in exploring the properties of **C-nBFI** of different sizes. Here we report on a new series of **C-nBFI**, from the 3-mer to the 6-mer. DFT calculations predict the members of this series to display a variety of conformations depending on their size, from highly planar **C-3BFI** to saddle-shaped **C-5BFI** and figure-eight shaped **C-6BFI**, and these structures are further supported by spectroscopic measurements. We find that the conformation adopted directly affects the extent of global antiaromaticity, which is more pronounced for the smaller macrocycles. Nuclear Independent Chemical Shifts (NICS) calculations suggest global antiaromaticity for the relatively planar **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** in the neutral state, and global aromaticity in the dicationic state, whereas local aromaticity prevails for larger and less conjugated **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI**. The smaller **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** also show significantly different photophysical behavior, with weak and broad $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ emission bands, whereas the nonplanar **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI** show strong $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ emission bands. Transient absorption measurements support the non-radiative emission pathway for **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** monomers, with sharp transient

$S_1 \rightarrow S_n$ bands, whereas for the more flexible **C-5BFI**, several conformations result in broad absorption.

Scheme 1. Structures of cyclic α, α' -oligothiophenes (**nT**) and of the linear (**L**) and macrocyclic (**C**) α, α' -oligofurans (**nBFI**) discussed in this work. **R** = 2-octyldodecyl.^[16]

Results and Discussion

Synthesis

The oligofuran macrocycles were synthesized from dibromobifuran-carboximide **1** as described in Scheme 2, using the nickel-catalysed Yamamoto coupling^[17] method under high dilution conditions (1.3 mM).^[13] The macrocycles were purified as a mixture and separated using gel permeation chromatography (GPC) to yield **C-3BFI** (4%), **C-4BFI** (31%), and a mixture of **C-5BFI** (11%) and **C-6BFI** (14%) that required an additional GPC separation step. The structures of the macrocycles were confirmed using MALDI-TOF, ¹H-NMR, and ¹³C-NMR.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of **C-nBFI**. Conditions: Ni(COD)₂, 2,2'-bipyridine, tetrahydrofuran (THF), room temperature, 48 h. COD = 1,5-cyclooctadiene; **R** = 2-octyldodecyl.

Structure

To elucidate the structural features of the macrocycles, **C-nBFI** ($n = 3-6$) were optimized at the B3LYP/6-311G(d) level. The number

of repeating units directly correlates with the observed conformations adopted by the macrocycles to minimize strain. Minimal strain should be obtained when the bisecting angle for each **BFI** unit is 81° (Figure S56, ESI). The smallest macrocycle, **C-3BFI**, is rigid, planar, and the most strained in the series, with a strain energy of 7.5 kcal mol⁻¹ (Figure 1b). By contrast, **C-4BFI** has two conformers, one nearly planar and the other saddle-shaped (bent by 27° out of plane, Figure S57, ESI), that are separated by a negligible energy difference (0.2 kcal mol⁻¹).^[14] The larger macrocycles, **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI**, can bend and twist to release the macrocyclic strain, and they converge (regardless of the starting conformation) to a saddle-shaped conformer for **C-5BFI** and a figure-eight shape for **C-6BFI** (Figure 1a). The figure-eight conformer arises from two of the bonds between the bifuran imide subunits flipping from *syn* to *anti*, which is a feature only observed for **C-6BFI**.^[18] Variable temperature ¹H-NMR of **C-6BFI** shows a singlet in the aromatic region at room temperature, which broadens upon cooling, eventually resulting in three distinct singlets (Figure S12). These are the singlets corresponding to the *D*₂ symmetry expected for a figure eight macrocycle. The broadening observed for **C-6BFI** corresponds to fast exchange, with a coalescence temperature of -5°C, and energy barrier of 13.0 kcal mol⁻¹ (see Figure S12 and Equation S1 in ESI). This energy barrier is too high to attribute to simple bending and twisting of a double bond; instead, it suggests a process that requires much more energy, such as the flip of a strained macrocyclic bond from *anti* to *syn*. In contrast, cooling of **C-5BFI** does not result in significant spectral changes.

For the smaller **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** macrocycles, the energy differences between the constrained planar (*D*_{nh}) conformations and the optimal structures were found to be well within the margin of error for the calculation (< 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹), indicating that, in solution at room temperature, the conformations of both macrocycles are highly likely to be planar on average. In contrast, with energy differences of 20 kcal mol⁻¹ and 93 kcal mol⁻¹ for **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI**, respectively, the likelihood of these larger macrocycles adopting a planar conformation is extremely low.

Figure 1. (a) Optimized structures for **C-nBFI-H** ($n = 3-6$, left to right). (b) Calculated (B3LYP/6-311G(d)) strain energy per unit for **C-nBFI-H**. (c) Experimental (black, **R** = 2-octyldodecyl) and computational (red, **R** = H) chemical shifts of **C-nBFI-R**. (d) HOMO-LUMO gaps for optimized structures (red) and *D*_{nh}-restricted structures (blue) of **C-nBFI**, and for optimized structures of **L-nBFI** (green). The optimal and *D*_{nh}-restricted structures of **C-3BFI** are nearly identical, and therefore overlap in their HOMO-LUMO gaps.

GMMX calculations support these findings: all 451 conformers of **C-6BFI** within ± 3.5 kcal mol⁻¹ of the optimized structure were figure-eight shaped (Figure 2b and Figure S42, ESI). For **C-5BFI**, the GMMX calculations yielded 15 conformers within ± 3.5 kcal mol⁻¹ of the optimized structure, none of which were planar (Figure 2a and Figure S38, ESI).

To gain more insight into the structural aspects of the conformational features of **C-nBFI**, we investigated the calculated and experimental NMR data. The ¹H-NMR spectra of the **C-3BFI** to **C-6BFI** series differ mainly in the chemical shift of their β protons (Figure 1c), which ranges from 6.97 ppm (**C-3BFI**) to 7.47 ppm (**C-5BFI**). Calculated NMR chemical shifts show the same trend as the experimentally measured shifts (Figure 1c). The chemical shift increases as the macrocycle size increases from the trimer to pentamer before slightly decreasing again for **C-6BFI**. This change stems mainly from the differences in the distances between the β -protons of neighboring **BFI** units, as we demonstrate for the dimer model (see section S4.6, ESI). Overall, there is good correlation between the experimental and calculated chemical shifts of the conformers after optimization.

Figure 2. (a) Overlay of all 15 structures of **C-5BFI** obtained from GMMX. (b) Overlay of 448 structures of **C-6BFI** obtained from GMMX. Three additional figure-eight-shaped structures were omitted from the overlay for clarity (because their positions were translated in relation to those of the other structures). All 451 conformers were figure-eight shaped

C-3BFI was crystallized by slow evaporation in benzene and acetonitrile, to yield orange crystals. The structure was solved by X-ray crystallography in triclinic space group P-1 with 4 molecules per asymmetric unit (see Section S6 in the ESI). The core of the macrocycle is well defined, while the alkyl groups are partially disordered, (Figure 3a). The macrocycle cores are slightly bent, with interring dihedral angles ranging from 1.8°–13.0° (Figure 3b). The inner diameter of **C-3BFI** is 5.0 Å, corresponding to a van der Waals (vdW) cavity of 1.9 Å. This is similar in both size and shape to 18-crown-6 ether. For comparison, the inner diameter and corresponding vdW cavity for **C-4BFI** is 7.3 Å and 4.3 Å, respectively.^[14] The macrocycles are arranged in pairs, where within each pair the macrocycles are slipped stacked, with a nearly planar packing (the angle between two planes ranges between 4.5° to 7.5°). The shortest distance between the macrocyclic backbone to the plane of the nearly-parallel macrocycle is 3.2 Å. The packing of **C-3BFI** reveals two sets of double ribbons that run nearly orthogonal to each other leaving 63% voids in the structure. These voids are arranged as continuous channels some of which may be occupied by the unmodeled alkyl chains (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. X-ray structure of **C-3BFI**. (a) Ellipsoid representation drawn at 50% probability, (b) side view of two macrocyclic cores and (c) packing viewed along the a axis. 2-octyldodecyl and hydrogens were omitted for clarity.

HOMO and LUMO Energies

The HOMO and LUMO energies are directly related to π -orbital overlap in the conjugated backbone, which is in turn related to backbone planarity.^[19] The calculated HOMO–LUMO gap can therefore be used to test the relation between structure and conjugation by comparing the optimized structures of **C-nBFI** (Figure 1d, red) with the D_{nh} -constrained structures (Figure 1d, green) and with the structure of the equivalent **L-nBFI** (Figure 1d, blue). When plotted against $1/n$, both linear and D_{nh} -constrained macrocycles yield a linear fit (green and blue lines), as is expected for oligomers of increasing length.^[20] With the exception of the HOMO–LUMO gap of **C-3BFI** (which has near- D_{3h} symmetry in the optimized structure), the HOMO–LUMO gaps of the **C-nBFI** macrocycles do not fit either of the trends. **C-4BFI** is predicted to have a lower gap than the corresponding linear oligomer, and a higher gap than D_{4h} symmetry offers, consistently with decreased conjugation due to bending of the macrocyclic backbone. Interestingly, the HOMO–LUMO gaps of **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI** are not only higher than those of the D_{nh} -constrained structures, but also higher than those of their linear counterparts. This observation offers an important insight into their conjugation: it suggests that both these larger macrocycles are distorted to a degree that offsets any increase in conjugation gained from the closure of the linear oligomer into a macrocycle.

Global and Local Aromaticity

To explore the aromaticity of **C-nBFI** of different sizes and in different oxidation states, we calculated the anisotropy of the current (induced) density (ACID)^[21] and conducted NICS analyses.^[22] Plots of the calculated ACID values (Figure 4) use the current density (yellow surface) and the current density vectors (overlaid by blue arrows for clarity) as a method of quantifying π -conjugation and, if present, paratropic and diatropic ring currents, where counter-clockwise current vectors indicate a paratropic ring current (antiaromatic system), and clockwise vectors indicate a diatropic current (aromatic system). The ACID plots show a global antiaromatic ring current for **C-3BFI** (Figure 4a) along the C_a - C_a -O pathway, with local aromatic current for the

Figure 4. ACID plots for (a) **C-3BFI**, (b) **[C-3BFI]²⁺**, (c) **C-4BFI**, (d) **[C-4BFI]²⁺**. Current density vectors (overlaid with blue arrows for clarity) indicate diatropic (clockwise) and paratropic (counter-clockwise) ring current (red arrows, added for clarity)

furan subunits. Compound **C-4BFI** (Figure 4c), which is slightly bent, still shows global antiaromaticity, but with lower current density. By contrast, **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI** (Figures S31–32, ESI) show no global ring current (*i.e.*, no response to the magnetic field) in either the clockwise or counter-clockwise direction.

The counter-clockwise (global antiaromatic) ring current of **C-3BFI** (Figure 4a) flips to become a clockwise (aromatic) ring current upon formation of the dication **C-3BFI²⁺** (Figure 4b), with this flip located on the carbon backbone (C_{α} - C_{β} - C_{β} - C_{α}). The plot also shows an increase in charge delocalization for the dication, with similar flipping behaviour observed between **C-4BFI** and **C-4BFI²⁺** (Figure 4c,d). NICS calculations can be used to estimate aromaticity based on the existence and effect of a ring current inside the conjugated system: negative NICS values (blue) indicate an aromatic system, whereas positive (red) values suggest an antiaromatic system. Figure 5 shows a map of the zz components 1 Å above the average molecular plane of the neutral and dicationic forms of **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI**. The NICS(1) plots fully support the observations from the ACID plots: the aromaticity of the furan subunits is maintained in the dicationic form, with the aromaticity of the macrocycle (as indicated by the color in the center of the map) flipping from positive (red) values in the neutral form (Figure 5a,c) to negative (blue) values in the dication (Figure 5b,d). Consistently with the ACID plots, global antiaromaticity is more pronounced in **C-3BFI** (Figure 5a) compared with **C-4BFI** (Figure 5c), which may result from the latter macrocycle's larger size reducing the effect on the center as well as from deviation of the molecule from planarity.

The NICS values for the global aromatic current cannot be applied for comparison with the nonplanar **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI**, where σ orbitals can be involved. In addition, comparison of ring current for different sizes will necessarily result in different NICS values, as the distance from the dummy atom varies. To overcome these factors, and monitor the effect of conformation on the global aromaticity, we monitored the NICS(1) values for each furan ring (Figure 6, red).

The NICS(1) values decrease from planar **C-3BFI** to saddle-shaped **C-5BFI**, which indicates increased local aromaticity as the deviation from planarity increases. The values were compared with the corresponding linear **nBFI**, which showed no change with increasing length (Figure 6, blue).^[23] The reduction in local aromaticity with increasing planarity for **C-nBFI** can be accounted to increasing contribution of the global antiaromatic ring current. In addition to the calculated NICS values, the global (anti)aromatic ring current can be observed experimentally by examining the ¹H-NMR spectra of **C-nBFI**. As the macrocycle deviates from

planarity with increasing size, the β -protons display a downfield shift, and the calculated chemical shifts for these protons show an identical trend (Figure 1c). Differences between the geometries of the molecules in the series may contribute to the observed chemical shifts, but cannot fully account for them, so other factors must also be considered (see discussion in section S4.6. in ESI). Global (anti)aromaticity in π -conjugated macrocycles was previously observed for neutral porphyrinoids^[24] and charged porphyrin nanorings,^[9a] but is rarely observed in other neutral macrocycles. The global (anti)aromaticity observed in the current systems is facilitated by the strong quinoid character of furans, which results in reduced local aromaticity compared with other macrocyclic systems.

Figure 5. Nuclear Independent Chemical Shift (NICS(1)_{zz}) plots for (a) **C-3BFI-H**, (b) **[C-3BFI-H]²⁺**, (c) **C-4BFI-H**, and (d) **[C-4BFI-H]²⁺**. Negative NICS values (blue) indicate an aromatic system, whereas positive (red) values suggest an antiaromatic system.

Figure 6. NICS(1) values averaged for all furan subunits in **C-3-6BFI** (red) and for the innermost furan subunit of their linear analogues **L-3-6BFI** (blue). The purple spheres represent the dummy atoms, located 1 Å above the plane.

Photophysical Properties

The structural differences between **C-nBFI** macrocycles of different sizes are expected to be reflected in their absorption spectra; a planar **C-nBFI** macrocycle should be centrosymmetric, in which case the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition would be symmetrically forbidden. In practice, we find that the Laporte-forbidden transitions are expressed as weak bands that intensify as the flexibility of the macrocycles increases. The absorption spectrum of **C-3BFI** (Figure 7a, black trace), the smallest and most rigid and planar member of the series, shows sharp bands at 300–400 nm with resolved vibronic shoulders, corresponding to $S_0 \rightarrow S_n$ transitions ($n > 1$), with very weak absorbance at 400–550 nm. The emission spectrum (red trace), excited at 390 nm, displays very weak and broad emission at 630 nm. Excitation at 630 nm (Figure 6a, blue trace) matches the absorption spectrum (Figure 7a, black trace). The emission band at 630 nm was not affected by varying the temperature (Figure S16, see ESI), excluding the possibility of an excimer, leading us to conclude that this band corresponds to the forbidden $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition.

The emission spectra of **C-4BFI** (Figure 7b, red and blue traces) display a similar trend to the emission spectrum of **C-3BFI**, with a main band at 530 nm and a broad band around 660 nm, however, the emission is significantly stronger in **C-4BFI**, with a fluorescence quantum efficiency of 18%. The excitation spectra

demonstrate that, in a similar manner as for **C-3BFI**, the broader peak is a forbidden $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$, whereas a supramolecular assembly serves as the emissive species for the more intense emission at 530 nm (see discussion below). The absorption spectrum of **C-5BFI** (Figure 7c, black trace) is composed of a $S_0 \rightarrow S_n$ transition at 380 nm that overlaps with the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition, with the band arising from the $S_0 \rightarrow S_n$ transition being broader in **C-5BFI** compared with its smaller analogues. This is consistent with the abovementioned calculations, which indicate that, unlike in **C-4BFI**, the most stable conformers of these macrocycles are not centrosymmetric, and therefore no transitions are Laporte-forbidden. The spectrum of **C-5BFI** is blue-shifted relative to that of **C-4BFI**, which implies reduced π -orbital overlap as the structure deviates from planarity. The λ_{\max} of **C-6BFI** (Figure 7d) is red shifted compared with **C-4BFI** and shows vibronic progression. This is an indication of a rigid, but less conjugated structure for **C-6BFI** compared with **C-4BFI**, which is in line with our conformational analysis.

The emission and excitation spectra of **C-5BFI** and **C-6BFI** (Figure 7c and d) are also consistent with the non-planar conformation observed for the ground state. Indeed, the excitation spectra match the absorption spectra, which is an indication that the emitting species is the absorbing species, and also that no significant conformational changes occur in the excitation process. In this regard, **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** differ greatly from the larger macrocycles.

The S_1 state of **C-3BFI** is dark and the fluorescent quantum yield is negligible. In contrast, **C-5BFI** displays brighter S_1 state, but broad absorption and fluorescence bands. To gain better understanding of the excited state dynamics in these two different systems, we investigated both macrocycles using transient absorption (TA) spectroscopy.^[25] The TA spectrum of **C-3BFI** excited at 480 nm (Figure 8a) is highly structured, with a sharp absorption band at 580 nm (FWHM 30 nm) along with a weaker peak at 850 nm. The induced absorption decays uniformly to zero with a time constant of 1.3 ns demonstrating that relaxation is directly back to S_0 . Spectral cuts in a narrow range surrounding the 580 nm absorption spike also exhibit weak spectral oscillations tentatively assigned to excited state coherent vibrational motion introduced by impulsive excitation. Considering the absence of fluorescence, metastable intermediates or stable photoproducts, the 1.3 ns S_1 lifetime is assigned to internal conversion (IC).

Figure 7. Normalized absorption, emission, and excitation spectra of (a) **C-3BFI**, (b) **C-4BFI**, (c) **C-5BFI**, and (d) **C-6BFI**. “Ab.” denotes absorption spectra, For wavelength X as defined beneath the plots, “Em.X” denotes emission spectra excited at X nm, and “Ex.X” denotes excitation spectra with the emission wavelength set to X nm. Spectra measured in chloroform.

Figure 8. Magic angle transient absorption spectra of (a) **C-3BFI**, (b) **C-5BFI** all excited at 480 nm. Measured in in chloroform.

In contrast, prompt TA of **C-5BFI** following photo-excitation at 480 nm shows enhanced transmission below 530 nm and a broad and nearly structureless induced absorption with a mild peak at 930 nm (Figure 8b). Since fluorescence lies to the red of 530 nm the induced transmission is assigned to ground state bleaching (GSB). Another noteworthy difference between these macrocycles is the asymptotic TA spectrum. Unlike **C-3BFI** ring which decays non-radiatively to S_0 , of **C-5BFI** fluoresces with a significant ~40% quantum efficiency, at the end of which a long-lived metastable state is established. As demonstrated by a 10 ns TA spectrum, this product is characterized by induced absorption across the probed range with a broad peak at 850 nm. In light of the molecule's photo-stability this difference spectrum is assigned to absorption from the lowest triplet state. Thus, despite the significant probability of emission, a competitive channel of intersystem crossing (ISC), not seen for **C-3BFI**, is manifest here. The decay between these asymptotic states takes place in two stages. Over the first few tens of ps the 950 nm peak is diminished and concomitantly absorbance near 550 nm increases. Later the TA decays uniformly to that of the triplet with ~2 ns exponential kinetics (Figure S19).^[26]

The photophysical differences between **C-3BFI** and **C-5BFI** are consistent with the higher planarity and rigidity of the former. This explains the jump from negligible to efficient fluorescence stemming from a formally dark S_1 going from former the latter. It also matches the efficient ISC, and broad and structureless TA spectra for S_1 and T_1 in **C-5BFI**. The presence of significant ps restructuring in S_1 following impulsive excitation for **C-5BFI** but not for **C-3BFI** is again consistent with above trends. The TA

polarization anisotropy (Figure S24) and its changes with time are also in accord with these conclusions.

Conclusion

We have introduced the first synthesis and characterization of a series of oligofuran macrocycles. The properties of these macrocycles vary greatly with size: the cyclic trimer, **C-3BFI**, is planar and rigid as confirmed by its X-ray structure, displays only weak emission, and mostly decays via an internal conversion pathway. The tetramer, which shows slightly greater flexibility, is fluorescent and decays at least partly via the ISC pathway. **C-5BFI** is highly flexible and **C-6BFI** displays a figure-eight conformation as evidenced by both calculations and VT-NMR. NICS and ACID calculations indicate a transition from global antiaromaticity to local aromaticity with increasing macrocycle size, as a result of deviation from planarity. The decreasing global antiaromatic character is also evidenced experimentally from the NMR spectra. Overall, this study demonstrates the large versatility of macrocyclic oligofurans, with an increase of a single unit resulting in their displaying different conformations with different aromatic and photophysical properties. This study also provides evidence of experimentally observed global antiaromaticity in a neutral macrocycle.

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- [26] In order to clarify the source of enhanced vibronic structure in S₀ bleaching contribution to TA, a complimentary pump-probe experiment on **C-5BFI** was conducted exciting in the intense absorption band at 400 nm. While both experiments exhibit similar kinetics (Figure S21), the GSB range is blue-shifted, and the vibronic features are diminished. Despite these differences after a similar excited state decay time, ISC yields as attested to by the 850 nm absorption feature are nearly identical. Our understanding of these results is that ground state structural inhomogeneity in **C-5BFI** broadens the absorption spectrum. Pumping with a relatively narrow pulse centered at 480 nm selectively excites a certain subpopulation which leads to a structured bleach signal. This does not change the ultimate fate of excitation which is similar in terms of emission and triplet generation probabilities after excitation at both wavelengths (Figure S23).

Entry for the Table of Contents

A new series of macrocyclic furans demonstrate the effect of size on their conformation, global antiaromaticity, and photophysical properties.